

Teachers' Workload and Learners' Performance

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Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the teachers' workload and learners' performance. This study was conducted by 120 public secondary school teachers from grade 7 in 25 schools in District 1 for the school year 2024-2025. The descriptive research design was used. The study data showed that the students' grades in their 1st and 2nd quarters were taken from their advisers. The descriptive mean was used. The Mann-Whitney U Test was used to determine the significant difference between teachers in the areas of teaching load, administrative tasks, and student support when grouped and compared according to the variables. The Spearman's Rho Correlation Test was used to determine the significant relationship between teachers' workload and learners' performance. Using the self-made questionnaire and the students' 1st and 2nd quarter grades, the study focused only on determining the significant relationship between teachers' workload and learners' performance. The findings revealed a significant relationship between the teachers' workload and learners' performance. Further, the p-value or the correlation coefficient of 0.002 showed a significant relationship between teachers' workload and learners' performance. Teacher workload consistently recommends strategies like reducing marking, sharing work, implementing efficient feedback practices, and simplifying lesson planning to alleviate stress and improve well-being.

Keywords: Learner's Performance, Teacher's Workload, well being

Introduction:

The Department of Education (DepEd) has recently issued DepEd Order No. 5, s. 2024, titled "Rationalization of Teachers' Workload in Public Schools and Payment of Teaching Overload." According to Llego (2024), this innovative policy seeks to address the persistent problems related to teacher workload and compensation, focusing on overtime remuneration. This new issuance tackles grey areas such as workload regarding compensation, utilizing insights from the DepEd Order and the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers (RA 4670).

Teachers' tasks beyond instruction are said to affect teachers' well-being and students' academic performance because their focus and attention are divided. According to the study of Arañas (2023), teachers' duties are not directly related to teaching but are part of the school's operations and are regarded by teachers as "additional" tasks. Some consider these functions helpful in personal and professional development; however, time for instruction and family is sacrificed.

Heavy workloads, such as administrative tasks and extracurricular responsibilities, can negatively affect teachers' well-being. This, in turn, can impact their overall effectiveness in the classroom. Additionally, some studies suggest no direct link between teachers' ancillary workloads and students' academic performance; teachers' stress and reduced well-being can indirectly affect the learning environment (Guimary, 2023).

Since educators are leaders and the cornerstones of education, their workload is crucial since it influences the intended results for educators and students. According to this study, the amount of work teachers do over the school year is their workload. The tasks include course planning, instruction, testing, administrative tasks, and marking. Overwork prevents teachers from delivering quality instruction and effectively interacting with students. According to Jomud et al. (2020), workload influences teachers' performance. Too much administrative work has a "blanket" impact on every school setting, and it seriously threatens to take away teachers' professional concentration on instruction and student learning. The impact of too many administrative and official tasks related to system imperatives, such as requirements for complying with standardized reports and recording progress, including learner progress, has led to an increase in teachers' workload. The researcher felt there is a norm of silence in accepting

teachers' workload, regardless of their circumstances. Many times, in her recent memory, a "no" for an answer is as abhorrent as an answer could be. Without much freedom to refuse, there is a question about how ancillary workloads affect teachers' performance, ultimately influencing learners' academic performance.

Current State of Knowledge

Teachers' Workload. Teaching has become more difficult over the last twenty years due to increased paperwork, bureaucracy, and disruptive students. These factors comprise teaching students with low motivation, upholding classroom discipline, managing time constraints and workload pressures, navigating frequent changes, undergoing evaluations by others, facing challenging dynamics with colleagues and management, and contending with inadequate working conditions, role ambiguity, strained relationships with students and staff, and job instability (Hasan, 2020).

Numerous stressors are present for teachers. Since the Indonesian government issued a policy regarding the benefits of teacher certification, teachers' performance has been in the spotlight. To be certified as primary school teachers, teachers must fulfill a minimum of 24 hours per week, with a maximum limit of 40 hours per week. Teachers' workloads are governed by various laws to meet quality standards and enhance the quality of education. Teachers are thus seen as one of the groups that hold complete accountability for carrying out diverse governmental educational policies, especially regarding the practice and implementation of education at the level of school education units. Thus, one can gain insight into teacher performance by comprehending their workload.

Interestingly, instructors are expected to meet high standards for their workload (Yusuf et al., 2021). According to Hendriani (2022), teaching is a highly stressful profession. He claims that diligent teachers are constantly overworked and that their high stress levels are caused by their growing workload, variety of responsibilities, and huge class sizes. Teachers' roles as professionals will dictate how educational quality advances. They should therefore be given a burden that is proportionate to their ability to perform their jobs effectively, which will affect their competency.

According to numerous studies conducted across nations, teachers with a heavy workload will find it more challenging to organize, carry out, and assess lessons and mentor their pupils since they are stressed. According to Wakoli (2016), the growing body of research on the topic and the various workshops and programs created to assist teachers in managing the issue and lowering occupational stress have demonstrated that occupational stress associated with workload among teachers has become a growing concern. The situational expectations placed on the organization's personnel may be the source of workplace workload. These expectations may come from within the person or the work environment and associated features. According to Gul (2016), identifying needs, establishing objectives to meet those needs, and making plans to reach those goals constitutes time management. Time management is a global occurrence. Not only does it entail identifying needs and setting priorities, but it also entails the skill of organizing, planning, and allocating one's time to accomplish goals.

According to the relationship between teachers' workload and time management abilities, teachers who manage their time well can lessen their workload. Time management allows managers to develop solutions, plan for the future, and evaluate overall progress, but it does not solve management difficulties. In order to improve time management abilities and lessen teachers' workload, this research project will be crucial.

Programs for school-based management seek to enhance learning outcomes by enabling individuals most knowledgeable about school issues to develop solutions. However, few studies have used experimental techniques to test the efficacy of such programs. Programa Escuelas de Calidad is a school-based management program in Mexico. Researchers undertook a randomized evaluation to determine how it affects student performance. The program created and implemented school improvement plans using a combination of state funding and a cash award. After one year, there was no change in school performance due to the intervention.

Raising school performance, including test scores and attendance, remains a significant problem for communities in many nations. School-based management (SBM) policies are one tactic that seeks to transfer decision-making authority from the federal or state level to the schools themselves. Parents, educators, and school administrators are in charge of budgetary distribution, hiring personnel, curriculum development, and the acquisition of instructional supplies, among other things, under these policies. For several reasons, empowering local stakeholders, who are most suited to understand their school's issues and possible solutions, may enhance learning results. These include better resource management, more efficient administration, more staff and student involvement, and more equitable parent-teacher decision-making.

While several studies have examined how SBM programs affect test scores, dropout rates, and teacher and parent participation, relatively few have used experimental methods to assess SBM or the programs' long-term consequences.

As the primary mediator between educational policies and student experiences in the classroom, educational theory inextricably links teachers to student learning. Research continuously demonstrates a relationship between classroom

and teacher variables significantly impacting student outcomes (Fernandez, 2022). From an alternative perspective, Liebowitz (2020) thought that schools typically create HRM systems to promote employee work, allow for the acknowledgment and punishment of varying performance levels, and enhance abilities through feedback as part of the assessment procedure.

Theoretical Framework

The Multi-Unit Assignment Theory by Budish and Cantillon (2010) and the Theory of Performance (ToP) by Don Elger (2013) will be used as theoretical frameworks for this study. Harvard Business School developed the Multi-Unit Assignment Theory to study the drafting mechanism for allocating courses. The theory is grounded on workloads that can be manipulated in both theory and practice, but it was later proven that these manipulations were causative of welfare losses. Nonetheless, it was discovered that welfare exceeds that of its widely examined strategy-proof alternative. We uncover a novel connection between fairness and welfare that accounts for the draft's good performance despite the expenses incurred by strategic behavior, and we subsequently create a new draft that minimizes these costs.

Looking at the theory closely, it resembles distributing non-specialized assignments through ancillary functions among teachers. Relative to this theory, ancillary functions may look productive if drawn on board but may cause overwork or over-assignment to teachers, which is, in fact, counter-productive.

Also, schools commonly limit the number of students per class, and these class-size limits create an instance of a multi-unit assignment problem. If it is not possible for all students to take their most desired schedule of courses, it creates a question of how seats should be allocated in every course. Other examples of multi-unit assignment problems include assigning tasks to shifts to workers, sports team players, sharing resources to its users, and airport takeoff and landing slots.

Assignment theory dictates which resources are allocated to specific departments, machines, or operation centers during production. The aim is to allocate resources to increase production efficiency, manage costs, and optimize profits. According to assignment theory, the allocation is optimal when workers are allocated top-down according to their skills, whereby the most competent worker is assigned to the most complex job and the least competent worker is assigned to the simplest job.

Moreover, this theory is based on Elger's Theory of Performance (ToP) to elucidate performance and performance enhancements. To perform means to yield results that are valued. A performer may refer to either a person or a group working together. Performance development is a journey, with the performance level indicating the journey's position. The current performance level is determined holistically by six (6) components: context, knowledge level, skill levels, identity level, personal factors, and fixed factors (Nyanza, 2015).

The theory of performance is helpful in many learning contexts, especially in the present study, since high-level performers produce accomplishments. The traditional context of the performance theory informs learning in classrooms, workshops, and other venues traditionally associated with learning.

The measurements of this theory give a gateway to understanding all aspects related to performance, their applicability, and relevance to the function of management generally and procurement specifically. The theory of performance applies to this study because the field of procurement is dynamic. This field has evolved, including being considered formidable in organizational undertakings, both private and public. It has gained recognition as a professional function (Nyanza, 2015).

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of teachers' workload and learners' performance in one of the districts of a medium-sized division in Central Philippines for the First and Second quarters of the School Year 2024-2025.

Methodology:

This section presents the study's methodology, including the research design, and respondents of the study, the data gathering instruments, which include the test of its validity and reliability, the data gathering procedures, the analytical schemes, and the statistical tools used to treat the data.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design. A scientific method known as the descriptive research design entails observing and detailing a subject's behavior while ensuring it remains unaltered. Descriptive research is frequently employed as a precursor to quantitative research designs, and the general overview provides valuable insights into which variables are worth testing quantitatively (Shuttleworth, 2021). Descriptive research aims to

describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically. Descriptive research is an appropriate choice when the research seeks to identify characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories (McCombes, 2020). Descriptive research design is valuable to this study as it provides facts and scientific judgment. Also, this design is appropriate for the study as it helps reveal patterns and connections that might otherwise go unnoticed, present situations, and determine the prevailing issues, making adequate and accurate interpretation of the data.

Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents were the 120 public secondary school teachers from grade 7 distributed in 25 schools in District 1. Since the total number of respondents was easily manageable, the researcher used a purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling method, involves intentionally selecting units according to predetermined criteria. Qualitative research serves the purpose of selecting a particular group of individuals or units for analysis. Non-random selection, small sample sizes, and an emphasis on particular traits characterize purposive sampling. It is also called judgmental or selective sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2023).

Data Gathering Instrument

To determine the level of teachers' workload, the researcher used a self-made data-gathering instrument subjected to Validity and Reliability testing. The said instrument consisted of two parts:

The first part gathered the respondents' data, which includes age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service.

Part 2 contained the questionnaire proper. There will be a total of 10 line items for teaching load, student support, and administrative tasks, or a total of 30 line items.

The respondents were asked to rate each line item with a numerical score described as 5, being the highest with a description of "Always," 4 as "Often," 3 as "Sometimes," 2 as "Rarely," and 1 as "Almost Never".

Validity

Validity is defined as the extent to which a concept is accurate. The extent to which the interpretations of a test's results are justified is known as validity, depending on the specific purpose for which the test is designed (Carlson, 2020). Since the instrument for this study is a self-made questionnaire, its validity was established. The proposed questionnaire was subjected to face and content validation by a group of 3 validators who are considered academic and qualified experts. For this study, the three chosen validators are as follows: the first validator has a PhD degree in Educational Management and is currently assigned as Principal 1 in the same SDO. The second validator is a Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management and works as an Education Program Supervisor in the same division. The third validator is a Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management, currently working as a Public Schools District Supervisor in the same division of Research.

Based on the criteria Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates set forth, the five-point scale will be established to rate each item's validity (Morgan, 2018). The Mean Score Range from 4.21-5.00 with Verbal Interpretation of "Excellent", 3.41-4.20 "Very Good", 2.61-3.40 "Good", 1.81-2.60 "Fair," and 1.00-1.80 as "Poor".

The result of the validation of the research instrument was 4.89, interpreted as "Excellent", which showed that the validity of the research instrument was valid.

Reliability

Reliability pertains to the degree of consistency in scores or responses across different administrations of a measurement tool and among various sets of items (Bueno, 2016). Therefore, the self-made questionnaire was subjected to a reliability test to ensure the research instrument's accuracy, stability, and predictability.

The instrument's reliability was determined after assessing the questionnaire's validity and integrating all jury and panel members' corrections and suggestions. The dry-run involved 30 teachers from another district within the aforementioned large division, located in a highly urbanized area of central Negros. These teachers are not part of the sample set selected for the study. Subsequently, Cronbach's Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability index of the questionnaire.

Cronbach's Alpha estimates test reliability as the test score's internal consistency or inter-item homogeneity. Cronbach's alpha is an estimator of test reliability suitable for single-test applications, typically in cross-sectional designs. Given a test composed of p items, Cronbach's Alpha assumes that all items are equivalent test units and corresponds to the reliability of the whole test computed by extending the properties of one unit p times (Forero, 2021). Values of Cronbach's Alpha that are 0.7 or greater suggest acceptable internal consistency (Taber, 2020). The reliability index will be interpreted using the reliability coefficient interpretation guide as per the verbal description developed by J. P. Guilford.

The computed alpha was 0.942, interpreted as "Excellent". This implies that the research instrument is reliable for the study.

Data-Gathering Procedure

In conducting this study, the researcher took the following steps to gather the needed information and data: First, a letter was submitted to the Schools' Division Office asking permission to conduct the study and was addressed to the School's Division Superintendent. The approved letter was duplicated for distribution to the twenty-five (25) School Heads within the district where this study was conducted.

The data-gathering instrument was distributed outside school hours, not to distract the teachers from their regular school routine. The respondents were allowed 3 days to answer and return the hard copies of the instrument. Accomplished data gathering instruments were encoded and tallied to the pre-formatted Excel file for easier tabulation.

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software processed the calculation. Similarly, statistical tables were created based on the objectives outlined in the study.

Research Ethics Protocols

It is crucial to safeguard human subjects in all research studies by applying suitable ethical principles. Ethical considerations are especially significant in qualitative studies because of the study process's in-depth nature. According to the principle of voluntary participation, individuals should not be forced to participate in research (Trochim, 2021). Consent was granted freely (voluntarily), participants should comprehend what is being requested, and involved individuals must be competent to consent.

This indicates that potential research participants have received complete information regarding the procedures and risks associated with the research and are required to consent to participate (Trochim, 2021). For individuals to participate in a research study, they need to be sufficiently informed about the research, understand the details, and be free to choose whether to join or opt out. Only after thoroughly explaining the research process was the participants' consent to participate in this study secured. Thus, participants were fully informed about all research procedures and encouraged to participate by signing a consent form.

Analytical Schemes

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive-analytical scheme to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service.

Objective No. 2 also used a descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of teachers' workload in the area regarding Teaching Load, Student Support, and Administration Task.

Objective No. 3 also used a descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of teachers' workload when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 4 used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of learners' performance.

Objective No. 5 used the comparative analytical scheme to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of teachers' ancillary workload when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 used the relational analytical scheme to determine if there is a significant relationship between teachers' workload and learners' performance.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following specific procedures to give the exact data and solution to each problem.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Variables Age, Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 2
Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 39 years old)	56	46.7
	Older (39 years old & above)	64	53.3
Sex	Male	51	42.5
	Female	69	57.5
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Bachelor's Degree)	35	29.2
	Higher (Master's & Doctorate Degrees)	85	70.8
Length of Service	Shorter (below 12 years)	56	46.7
	Longer (12 years & above)	64	53.3
Total		120	100.00

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age, where 56 or 46.7% were younger (below 39 years old), and equally, 64 or 53.30% were older (39 years old and above). Regarding sex, 51 or 42.50% were male

and 69 or 57.5% were female. Regarding the highest educational attainment, 35 or 29.2% belonged to lower respondents, and 85 or 70.8% belonged to higher respondents. Furthermore, according to length of service, 56 or 46.7% were categorized as shorter tenure respondents (below 12 years) and 64 or 53.3% as longer tenure respondents (12 years and above).

Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Teaching Load, Student Support, and Administrative Tasks

Table 3

Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Teaching Load

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
handle classes on prescribed schedule.	3.91	High
prepare DLL/DLP and stick to said plan in delivering lesson contents,	4.25	High
dedicate ample time preparing for visual aids.	3.89	High
conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs.	4.55	Very High
conduct timely assessments to validate pupils' learnings.	3.89	High
provide remedial classes whenever necessary or needed.	4.32	High
provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners.	3.77	High
provide activities intended for learners with special needs.	3.95	High
prepare timelines for all academic reports.	4.15	High
manage classroom rules for effective transfer of learning.	4.19	High
Mean	4.09	High

Table 3 shows the level of teachers' workload in teaching. The overall mean score is 4.09, interpreted as "high level". Item No. 4 obtained the highest mean score of 4.55, which states "conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs," interpreted as "very high level". Item No. 7 got the lowest mean score of 3.77, which states "provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners" as "high level". Teachers use enrichment and reinforcement activities to support at-risk learners, helping them develop their skills and knowledge while fostering a positive learning environment. Enrichment activities expand learning beyond the core curriculum, while reinforcement techniques, like positive feedback and rewards, help students to stay motivated and engaged. The result showed that teachers may not always prioritize or have the time to implement enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners. This can be due to various factors, such as time constraints, lack of resources, or a focus on standardized testing.

However, these activities are crucial for helping at-risk learners succeed academically and socially. Teachers often have limited time to prepare and implement these activities, especially with a large class size. Schools may not have the necessary materials or funding to support enrichment and reinforcement activities. Administrators must provide teachers with the resources and time to implement enrichment and reinforcement activities. Teachers should prioritize these activities and find creative ways to implement them, even with limited resources. Parents must support teachers by providing resources and volunteering time to help at-risk learners. The influence of workload on teachers' efficiency and students' academic achievement in public sector universities cannot be ignored. Universities must manage teacher workload and ensure educators have the resources to educate their students effectively (Balang, 2021). This includes providing teachers adequate training, resources, and support, reducing administrative burdens, and addressing root causes of stress and burnout. By doing so, universities can help to improve the overall quality of education and ensure that students receive the best possible learning experience. In a global context, the impact of workload on teacher efficiency and student achievement is a growing concern.

Table 4

Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Student Support

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
ensure that every student is assisted with various academic needs.	3.94	High
provide individual or group coaching as may be needed.	4.27	High
encourage learners to join co-curricular activities in school.	3.99	High
Call parents and inform them of the status of their children's performance in school.	4.51	Very High
provide differentiated instructions for slow-paced learners.	3.96	High
give preferential attention to students who are differently abled.	4.54	Very High
check on learners' weak and strong learning points so I could easily provide the appropriate teaching strategy.	3.84	High
teach children how to read and write outside of school hours.	3.95	High
gather all learners who are non-numerate or poor performers in Math so I could teach them as a group.	4.03	High
personally assess students' learning curves prior to grade level promotion.	4.16	High

Mean 4.12 High

Table 4 shows the level of teachers' workload in student support. The overall mean score is 4.12, interpreted as "high level". Item No. 6 obtained the highest mean score of 4.54, which states "give preferential attention to students who are differently abled," interpreted as "very high level". Item No. 7 got the lowest mean score of 3.84, which states "check on learners' weak and strong learning points so I could easily provide the appropriate teaching strategy," interpreted as "high level".

Teachers experience varying workload levels in supporting students, encompassing tasks beyond traditional instruction like lesson planning, assessment, discipline, and record-keeping. Excessive workload can lead to stress, burnout, and negatively impact teacher well-being and student outcomes. Teachers should emphasize various assessment methods to identify a learner's strengths and weaknesses and provide appropriate teaching strategies. This includes formal and informal assessments, such as standardized tests, quizzes, class participation observations, and one-on-one discussions. Continuous assessment throughout the learning process provides ongoing feedback to both teacher and student, allowing for adjustments in teaching strategies. Specifically, diagnostic assessments help identify student understanding in real-time, guiding instruction accordingly. Assessments that provide feedback during the learning process, which the teacher must observe, help identify areas where students struggle and excel. Examples include exit tickets, quick quizzes, and observing student engagement during class discussions. Teachers must be responsible for record-keeping, administering timetables, and evaluating student performance. Teachers should dedicate additional time and effort to supporting students struggling academically or behaviorally. Teachers can improve their time management skills to prioritize tasks and allocate time effectively.

The impact of teacher workload on students can be significant. Teachers who are overworked and stressed are less effective at delivering instruction, resulting in lower levels of student engagement and academic achievement. Students may also lack personalized attention and feedback, reducing motivation and academic performance (Afzal & Rafiq, 2022; Kamran, Afzal & Rafiq, 2022).

Table 5
Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Administrative Tasks

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
accept grade level chairmanship.	3.88	High
prepare campaign materials for <i>Brigada Eskwela</i>	4.40	High
work with various school organizations as adviser.	3.98	High
help in the implementation of the Wash-in-School program.	4.35	High
work with co-teachers and parents for the school feeding program.	4.01	High
help address bullying issues in school.	4.40	High
join in the school's community extension program.	3.92	High
provide support to the advocacies of our school leadership like in sports programs or culture and the arts.	3.95	High
assist in some fund-raising activities for the school.	4.14	High
connect with benefactors to provide ample school support.	4.13	High
Mean	4.12	High

Table 5 shows the level of teachers' workload in administrative tasks. The overall mean score is 4.12, interpreted as "high level". Items Nos. 2 and 6 obtained the highest mean score of 4.40, which states, "prepare campaign materials for Brigada Eskwela and help address bullying issues in school" interpreted as "very high level". Item No.1 got the lowest mean score of 3.88, which states "accept grade level chairmanship," interpreted as "high level". Teachers face a significant administrative workload beyond classroom teaching. While DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024, aims to alleviate this, many administrative tasks still exist, potentially impacting teachers' time for instructional preparation and student feedback. The extent of this workload and its impact on teacher well-being and performance vary depending on the school and individual circumstances. Teachers are responsible for teaching and administrative tasks like record-keeping, report generation, and communicating with parents. These tasks can be time-consuming and burdensome, potentially impacting teachers' ability to focus on their primary duty of teaching. A heavier administrative workload can lead to less lesson planning and student feedback time.

According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), teachers in many countries face high levels of workload, which can lead to stress, burnout, and reduced effectiveness in the classroom (Szabó, Kóródi, Szél & Jagodics, 2022). OECD has suggested that policymakers take steps to reduce teacher workload, like improving the efficiency of administrative tasks and providing more opportunities for professional development (Rafiq, Afzal & Kamran, 2022)

Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Teaching Load, Student Support, and Administrative Tasks when grouped according to Variables Age, Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 6
Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Teaching Load when Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>				
handle classes on prescribed schedule.	3.91	High	3.92	High
prepare DLL/DLP and stick to said plan in delivering lesson contents,	4.35	High	4.15	High
dedicate ample time preparing for visual aids.	3.96	High	3.82	High
conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs.	4.60	Very High	4.51	Very High
conduct timely assessments to validate pupils' learnings.	3.94	High	3.84	High
provide remedial classes whenever necessary or needed.	4.33	High	4.31	High
provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners.	3.73	High	3.81	High
provide activities intended for learners with special needs.	3.96	High	3.95	High
prepare timelines for all academic reports.	4.23	High	4.07	High
manage classroom rules for effective transfer of learning.	4.25	High	4.14	High
Mean	4.13	High	4.05	High

Table 6 indicates the level of teachers' workload in teaching load when grouped according to Age. The overall mean scores are 4.13 for the younger group, interpreted as a high level, and 4.05 for the older group, interpreted as a "high level". As assessed by the younger group, Item No. 4 got the highest mean score of 4.60, which states, "conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs. As assessed by the older group, Item No. 4 also got the highest mean score of 4.51, interpreted as very high, which states that a thorough profiling of students is needed to properly understand their individual learning needs. The level of teachers' workload in teaching load when grouped according to Age, both age groups got item No. 7 as the lowest mean, indicating that teachers emphasize providing activities to struggling learners less.

This implied that teachers were giving less priority to providing enrichment activities for at-risk learners. The results indicated that female teachers may experience a greater workload and stress levels than their male counterparts. This is due to more invisible tasks, emotional labor, and the fact that women often constitute much of the teaching workforce in many countries. While the exact nature and extent of these differences can vary, it is important to acknowledge the potential for gender-based disparities in teacher workload. Research indicates that female teachers may report higher stress levels, burnout, and exhaustion than male teachers. This can be attributed to the combined effects of workload, emotional demands, and potential social expectations. Heavy workloads may result in less time for discussion and interaction with teachers, making it harder to understand the material and engage with the course content.

This was validated by Berliner (2020), who stated that instructional quality is widely recognized as a strong determinant. Simply put, students learn because their teachers want them to learn. Thus, it is important to begin discussions with a reminder of what teaching and learning look like inside the different classrooms. Such clarification points to the teacher as not only the main source of learning but also the only point by which the 'control' for the learning process takes into force.

Table 7
Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Teaching Load when Grouped According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>				
handle classes on prescribed schedule.	3.88	High	3.94	High
prepare DLL/DLP and stick to said plan in delivering lesson contents,	4.19	High	4.28	High
dedicate ample time preparing for visual aids.	3.92	High	3.86	High
conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs.	4.68	Very High	4.46	High
conduct timely assessments to validate pupils' learnings.	3.96	High	3.84	High
provide remedial classes whenever necessary or needed.	4.35	High	4.30	High

provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners.	3.84	High	3.72	High
provide activities intended for learners with special needs.	3.94	High	3.97	High
prepare timelines for all academic reports.	4.15	High	4.14	High
manage classroom rules for effective transfer of learning.	4.31	High	4.10	High
Mean	4.06	High	4.12	High

Table 7 indicates the level of teachers' workload in teaching load when grouped according to sex. The overall mean scores are 4.06 for the male group, interpreted as "high level", and 4.12 for the female group, interpreted as "high level".

As the male and female groups assessed, Item No. 4 got the highest mean score of 4.68 and 4.46, which states "conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs," interpreted as "very high level". In contrast, Item No. 7 got the lowest mean score of 3.84 and 3.72, which states "provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners," interpreted as "high level".

This implied that teachers were giving less priority to providing enrichment activities for at-risk learners. The results indicated that female teachers may experience a greater workload and stress levels than their male counterparts. This is due to more invisible tasks, emotional labor, and the fact that women often constitute much of the teaching workforce in many countries. While the exact nature and extent of these differences can vary, it is important to acknowledge the potential for gender-based disparities in teacher workload. Research indicates that female teachers may report higher stress levels, burnout, and exhaustion than male teachers. This can be attributed to the combined effects of workload, emotional demands, and potential social expectations. Heavy workloads may result in less time for discussion and interaction with teachers, making it harder to understand the material and engage with the course content. Lack of support and timely feedback on assignments or the inability to answer questions outside of class can make it harder to succeed in the course. Students also noted that workload may be shifted onto them, making it challenging to balance other responsibilities like work or extracurricular activities (Junjie, 2020).

Table 8

Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Teaching Load when Grouped According to the Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>				
handle classes on prescribed schedule.	3.85	High	3.94	High
prepare DLL/DLP and stick to said plan in delivering lesson contents,	4.37	High	4.20	High
dedicate ample time preparing for visual aids.	4.00	High	3.84	High
conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs.	4.60	Very High	4.54	Very High
conduct timely assessments to validate pupils' learnings.	3.94	High	3.87	High
provide remedial classes whenever necessary or needed.	4.42	High	4.28	High
provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners.	3.80	High	3.76	High
provide activities intended for learners with special needs.	4.00	High	3.94	High
prepare timeline for all academic reports.	4.20	High	4.12	High
manage classroom rules for effective transfer of learning.	4.34	High	4.12	High
Mean	4.15	High	4.06	High

Table 8 shows the level of teachers' workload in terms of teaching load when grouped according to the highest educational attainment. The overall mean scores are 4.15 for the lower group, interpreted as "high level", and 4.06 for the higher group, interpreted as "high level".

As assessed by the lower and higher groups, item no. 4 got the highest mean score of 4.60 and 4.54, respectively, which states "conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their learning needs" interpreted as "very high level". In contrast, item no. 7 got the lowest mean score of 3.80 and 3.76, which states "provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners" interpreted as "high level".

Due to heavy workloads, teachers may struggle to provide individualized enrichment and reinforcement for at-risk learners. However, strategies like incorporating positive reinforcement, providing targeted group interventions, and

leveraging student data analytics can help bridge this gap. This may involve additional instruction outside the core curriculum, focusing on specific needs and providing extra support. When teachers are overworked and stressed, they may not be able to provide the same level of support and engagement, leading to a less practical learning experience. Heavy workloads may result in less time for discussion and interaction with teachers, making it harder to understand the material and engage with the course content. Lack of support and timely feedback on assignments or the inability to answer questions outside of class can make it harder to succeed in the course. Students also noted that the workload may be shifted onto them, making balancing other responsibilities like work or extracurricular activities challenging. Using data to identify struggling students and those with unique talents can help teachers tailor instruction and provide appropriate support.

In a demographic profile context, teaching and the type of work assigned to a teacher, including teaching hours, ancillary duties, and administrative tasks, are considered. These factors can be analyzed alongside demographic characteristics like age, experience, and education to understand how workloads impact teachers and potentially students. Students also reported feeling demotivated and disengaged from studies due to the lack of individualized attention and support from teachers. To address these issues, schools need to implement measures to reduce teacher workload, reduce the number of classes, and provide teaching assistants to help with the administrative tasks. Moreover, high workload levels can lead to teacher absenteeism, which can negatively impact students' academic achievement (Kamran, Afzal & Rafiq, 2022). To address these issues, schools may consider implementing measures such as reducing the number of the classes each teacher has to teach, providing teaching assistants to help with the grading and administrative tasks, and providing professional development opportunities to help teachers improve their skills and teaching methods (Rose & Sika, 2021).

Table 9
Level of Teachers' Workload in Teaching Load when Grouped According to the Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>				
handle classes on prescribed schedule.	3.91	High	3.92	High
prepare DLL/DLP and stick to said plan in delivering lesson contents, dedicate ample time preparing for visual aids.	4.35	High	4.15	High
conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs.	3.96	High	3.82	High
conduct timely assessments to validate pupils' learnings.	4.60	Very High	4.51	Very High
provide remedial classes whenever necessary or needed.	3.94	High	3.84	High
provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners.	4.33	High	4.31	High
provide activities intended for learners with special needs.	3.73	High	3.81	High
prepare timeline for all academic reports.	3.96	High	3.95	High
manage classroom rules for effective transfer of learning.	4.23	High	4.07	High
Mean	4.25	High	4.14	High
	4.13	High	4.05	High

Table 9 shows the level of teachers' workload in teaching load when grouped according to length of service. The overall mean scores are 4.13 for the lower group, interpreted as "high level", and 4.05 for the higher group, interpreted as "high level".

As assessed by shorter and longer group, Item No. 4 got the highest mean score of 4.60 and 4.51 respectively which states "conduct a thorough profiling of students to properly understand their individual learning needs" interpreted as "very high level", while Item No. 7 got the lowest mean score 3.73 and 3.81 and which states "provide enrichment and reinforcement activities for at-risk learners" interpreted as "high level". Teachers use enrichment and reinforcement activities to support at-risk learners by providing additional learning opportunities and positive reinforcement to help them succeed. Enrichment activities offer extended or enhanced learning experiences, while reinforcement strategies, like praise and rewards, create a supportive learning environment and motivate engagement. Providing specific praise for effort, offering tangible rewards for completing assignments, or creating a system of positive reinforcement like a check-in/check-out system. Enrichment activities can help at-risk learners develop important skills like critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration, which are crucial for success in and out of the classroom. A supportive learning environment and positive reinforcement can help at-risk learners develop a sense of confidence and self-esteem, which is essential for academic success and overall well-being.

The study found that when the teachers were overworked, they were less motivated to perform their duties, leading to decreased job satisfaction and efficiency. The impact of workload upon teachers' efficiency and their students' academic achievement has been studied extensively in various contexts. A study by Spoel and Velden (2020) found that high workload was associated with decreased well-being and job satisfaction among university teachers in Netherlands.

Table 10
Level of Teachers' Workload in the Area of Student Support when Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>				
ensure that every student is assisted with various academic needs.	3.94	High	3.93	High
provide individual or group coaching as may be needed.	4.28	High	4.26	High
encourage learners to join co-curricular activities in school.	4	High	3.98	High
Call parents and inform them of the status of their children's performance in school.	4.44	High	4.57	Very High
provide differentiated instructions for slow-paced learners.	3.92	High	4	High
give preferential attention to students who are differently-abled.	4.53	Very High	4.54	Very High
check on learners' weak and strong learning points so I could easily provide the appropriate teaching strategy.	3.78	High	3.89	High
teach children how to read and write outside of school hours.	4.01	High	3.90	High
gather all learners who are non-numerates or poor performers in Math so I could teach them as a group.	4.14	High	3.93	High
personally assess students' learning curves prior to grade level promotion.	4.12	High	4.20	High
Mean	4.12	High	4.12	High

Table 10 indicated the level of teachers' workload in student support when grouped according to length of age. The overall mean scores are 4.12 for both younger and older group, interpreted as "high level". As assessed by the younger and older groups, item 6 got the highest mean score of 4.53 for the younger group and 4.54 for the older group, which is interpreted as very high, stating, "Give preferential attention to differently-abled students.

Conclusion:

The study found that most teacher-respondents were female, older, had longer service, and attained higher education levels. Teachers reported a high level of workload in teaching, student support, and administrative tasks, which remained consistent across demographic variables. Learners' performance during SY 2024–2025 was rated very satisfactory, and a significant relationship was found between teachers' workload and student performance. The findings conclude that excessive teacher workload negatively affects teaching quality and student outcomes by limiting time for planning, research, and professional development, often leading to burnout, low self-esteem, and reduced well-being. Addressing this issue is crucial; schools should reduce workload by hiring additional staff, streamlining administrative tasks, and providing mental health support and professional development. Teachers are encouraged to practice time management, delegate tasks, collaborate, and maintain a healthy work-life balance to remain effective and positively impact learners and the community.

Acknowledgement

The researcher expresses heartfelt gratitude to all who contributed to the completion of this study through their valuable suggestions, encouragement, expertise, and unwavering support. Special appreciation is extended for the moral, financial, and emotional support that served as a constant source of motivation, as well as for the professional guidance and constructive feedback that greatly enhanced the quality of the research. Deep thanks are also given for the spiritual strength and wisdom that guided every step of this journey.

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